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Vol 4:3 2024

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ABSTRACT

For profit organizations recruiting and integrating workers with disabilities share a surprisingly common set of enablers. Across three different countries and five organizations, we find that they are characterized by (1) inclusive core values, (2) senior management commitment, (3) disability inclusive culture and (4) strong community partnerships. The study is based on a strategic selection of companies that employ a much larger proportion of employees with disabilities compared to similar companies in their country: Walgreens and Sephora in the USA, Philips and VodafoneZiggo in the Netherlands and Grundfos in Denmark. They are large, private, and successful companies in very different contexts. Our contribution to the disability literature is to focus on enablers rather than barriers to employment and to identify a specific set of common enablers that promote labor market inclusion of people with disabilities.

Keywords: Workplace inclusion, recruitment, for profit, disability employment, cross-national case study.

INTRODUCTION

People with disabilities are an untapped labor reserve that could assist in filling labor shortages, harnessing a broader skill set, creating inclusive workplaces and reducing government expenditures. But persons with disabilities experience numerous barriers to the labor market and significantly lower employment and higher inactivity rates compared to people without disabilities (OECD, 2010; WHO, 2011). When people with disabilities manage to find employment, they are more likely to work in precarious and atypical jobs (e.g., part time jobs, subsidized or supported employment) and find it more difficult to advance to management positions (Eurofound, 2021; Wilson-Kovacs et al., 2008).

The literature on disability and employment emphasise multiple internal and external barriers that hinder the full participation of people with disabilities in the labor market. The very idea of barriers is also inherent to the most common definitions of disability. In the UN Convention of Rights for Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006) and the WHO International Classification Model (WHO, 2011) persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or sensory impairments, which in interaction with environmental *barriers* may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others (UNCRPD, 2006: article 1).

The contribution of the current study is to identify enablers of disability in inclusive organizations by conducting comparative case-study research across different institutional contexts and examining whether these enablers are applicable when legislation and cultural contexts vary. To include more people with disabilities in the labor market, we need a better understanding of the enablers that make organizations inclusive for employees with disabilities (Collela & Bruyère, 2011; Seino et. al., 2017; Vornholt et. al., 2018). The research question is, therefore: Do organizations that employ a high percentage of disabled employees share a common set of characteristics across different institutional contexts?

In the following, we scope the relevant literature in different research fields to identify potential enablers of disability inclusive organizations. Second, we present the case design and methods of the study. Third, we present the cases and identify the common enablers across the cases. Finally, we discuss the findings, and how these enablers may transfer to other contexts to inspire other less disability inclusive work organizations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on disability and employment mainly focusses on barriers to the labor market inclusion of people with disabilities. This approach is in line with the social and relational models of disability and the idea that people with disabilities experience external barriers that hinder labor market inclusion (Oliver & Barnes, 2012; Shakespeare, 2014; Roulstone, 2014). The literature identifies several external barriers among employers, employment services and rehabilitation services, e.g., lack of information, bias, statistical discrimination, accessibility, stereotyping and inadequate resources (Borghouts-van de Pas & Freese, 2017). Barriers may even interact and accumulate (Frøyland et al., 2018).

In a literature review on (mental) disability and employment, Vornholt et al. (2018) identify both barriers and facilitators to employment, noting that there is far less empirical evidence of factors facilitating integration of people with disabilities, as research often focus on the identification of problems rather than on solutions. The main barriers identified in the review are co-workers and supervisors' attitudes and stereotypes, inadequate knowledge and experiences with disability, concerns about costs, training, and performance, increasing work demands and work intensity as well as low confidence and self-efficacy among people with (mental) disabilities.

We focus on the facilitators of labor market inclusion of people with disabilities and the enablers of disability inclusive company practices. Facilitators are enablers, i.e., mechanisms that promote labor market inclusion of persons with disabilities. Enablers are

like causal mechanisms, i.e., the conditions that are necessary and sufficient to explain a causal outcome (Goertz, 2006). Enablers are also like generative mechanisms, i.e., the active ingredients which are necessary to produce specific outcomes (Pawson, 2013). There are enablers on the supply, demand and support-side of the labor market, but in this article, we limit ourselves to explore the enablers on the demand-side, i.e., the mechanisms of disability inclusive work organizations.

Initially, we searched the scientific literature on disability and employment to identify previous research on enablers of disability inclusive work organizations. We searched in relevant disability journals, Web of Science and Google scholar for recent publications (2000 to 2024). We limited the search to company practices, work inclusion and disability. We included both quantitative and qualitative empirical studies. We found around 60 relevant publications that identified potential enablers of disability inclusive work organizations.

In the following, we summarize the main findings from this literature on the enablers of disability inclusive work organizations. Workplace studies of factors facilitating recruitment and inclusion of people with disabilities have been conducted within vocational rehabilitation and disability management (Bezyak et al., 2020; Bruyère, 2006; Harder & Scott, 2005). In general, the literature on the average effects of disability management interventions is contradictory. Gensby et al. (2014) found insufficient evidence to draw conclusions on the effectiveness of disability management programs, while Lefever et al. (2017) found sufficient evidence to conclude that disability management programs were effective and efficient.

When examining disability management, Chan et al. (2010) and Phillips et al. (2016) discovered that the organization's Disability Equity and Inclusion (DEI) policies and procedures were strongly associated with the employment of people with disabilities.

Bezyak et al. (2020) found that disability inclusion policies were the most important strategy and had the strongest correlation with actual recruitment. Gilbride et al. (2003) identified 13 characteristics within three broad categories (work culture, job match, and employer experience and support) and found that disability inclusive work organizations were characterized by leadership commitments trickling down to all levels of the organization, diversity and disability inclusion policies and procedures, a strong focus on ability not disability, and knowledge and experience providing job accommodation and workplace supports.

In a study on employment of people with disabilities in the post covid-19 economy, Chan et al. (2020) found 10 disability inclusion practices that were significantly associated with employment rates of people with disabilities in the workforce and emphasized the role of leadership/senior management. Boehm & Dwertmann (2015) emphasize three types of enabling moderators that facilitate positive disability effects in the workplace: (1) leadership behavior, (2) organizational climates and (3) human resources practices.

Hulsegge et al. (2022) compared inclusive and non-inclusive employers in the Netherlands. They found that inclusive organizations had more inclusive human resource practices, initiated more supportive human resources actions, adapted the working conditions more towards the needs of employees and negotiated more about work time and absenteeism. In a systematic review of workplace accommodation among persons with disabilities, Nevala et al. (2015) came to similar conclusions.

The role of senior management commitment and CSR policies is stressed as enablers of disability inclusive work organizations in several studies (cf. Bjørnshagen & Ugreninov, 2021; Dibben et al. 2002; Dibben & James, 2001; Dwertmann, 2016; Erickson et al., 2014; Houtenville & Kalargyrou, 2012). The moderating role of workplace culture and socialization to the workplace as well as experiences of workers with disabilities is also stressed in the literature (Collela, 1994; Lengnick-Hall, 2007; Collela & Bruyère,

2011; Wiggett-Barnard & Swartz, 2012; Hagner et al., 2014; Medina & Gamero, 2017). The literature on ‘Individual Placement and Support’ (IPS) emphasizes the importance of job design, job carving, and continuous job support (Drake & Bond, 2014; Suijkerbuijk et al., 2017).

It is important to note the discrepancy between what employers say (attitudes) and what they do (behavior) (Hulsegge et al., 2022). The majority of studies find that employers generally express positive attitudes to recruiting persons with disabilities, although some employers also express concerns about accommodation costs, fear of litigation, work performance and the qualifications of persons with disabilities (Burke et al., 2013; Graffam et al., 2002; Hernandez et al., 2000; Kaye et al., 2011; Morgan & Alexander, 2005; Unger, 2002; Waxman, 2015). Employer attitudes depend on several factors, including the type and severity of disabilities, perceived co-worker acceptance, previous experiences, knowledge of disability, accessibility of the workplace, perceived costs of accommodation, company policies and strategies as well as the size and sector of the employer (Gilbride et al., 2003; Gustafsson et al., 2014; Levy et al., 1992). However, studies of employer attitudes may be prone to social desirability bias (Kaye et al., 2011).

Field experiments and correspondence studies provide more reliable information about the recruitment practices of employers towards persons with disabilities (Baert, 2017; Riach & Rich, 2004; Rooth, 2014). The studies have found evidence of disability discrimination in recruitment by comparing call-back rates for (fictitious) applicants signaling either a disability or no disability. The studies find that jobseekers with disabilities are significantly less likely to be invited for job interviews compared to persons without disabilities (Ameri et al., 2018; Baert, 2016; Bellemare et al., 2018; Hipes et al., 2016; Stone & Wright, 2013; Krogh & Bredgaard, 2022). The extent of the penalty for disclosing a disability depends among other things on the national context, the type of disability and the type of job. Bredgaard (2018) connects employer attitudes with employer

practices and identify four types of employers: committed (positive attitudes and recruitment), passive (positive attitudes and non-recruitment), dismissive (negative attitudes and non-recruitment) and skeptical employers (negative attitudes and recruitment). In Denmark, 54 percent of employers were classified as passive employers, 22 percent as dismissive employers, 20 percent as committed employers, and the remaining 4 percent as skeptical employers. Similarly, Hemphill & Kulik (2016) differentiate between different types of employers in a study of recruitment practices towards people with disabilities in South Australia (antagonists, non-hirers, light-hirers, and loyal hirers). In a qualitative study of Swedish employers, Strindlund et al. (2019) identify three different views on employability, namely employability as constrained by disability, employability as independent of disability and conditional employability.

The main enablers of disability inclusive work organizations are summarized in the table below and classified at three different levels of the organization.

Table 1

Potential enablers of disability inclusive work organizations

<i>Level of the organization</i>	<i>Enabler</i>	<i>Description</i>
Individual	Positive attitudes	Positive attitudes among co-workers, supervisors and managers towards hiring and retaining persons with disabilities
	Knowledge of disability	Information about disability in general and compensation and accommodation opportunities in particular
	Experiences with disability inclusion	Previous (positive) experiences with hiring and retaining persons with disabilities
Management	Leadership commitment	Leadership and management commitment to disability inclusion
	Disability inclusion policies	Inclusion of disability in the organizations policies and procedures

	Disability inclusive HR practices	Human resource policies and practices that include disability employment, incl. training programs
	Job design and job support	Jobs and tasks that are suitable to employees with disabilities and a willingness to design jobs for persons with disabilities. Providing job coaches to support onboarding and alignment.
Organization	Inclusive culture	A culture and tradition for including persons with disabilities in the workplace
	Size, sector, job types	Larger organizations in (e.g., the public) sectors with job types that are suitable to persons with specific types of disabilities

This is not an extensive list of enablers, but the most common enablers found in the literature on disability inclusive work organizations. We will use this list to structure the data collection by searching for the potential enablers in the case studies and to compare the findings from the case studies.

METHODOLOGY

Our epistemology is a constructionist grounded theory approach that focuses on understanding the shared meanings from the respondents we interview (Charmaz, 2006). We take the viewpoint of the respondents and pull out their perceived meaning within a given environmental context (Crotty, 2003; Merriam, 2009). The sample criterion was to identify organizations with a strong reputation for recruiting and including people with disabilities in different national, policy and institutional contexts. We adopted the causes-of-effect approach to explanation by starting with cases and their outcomes and then moving backwards to examine their causes, i.e., enablers (Mahoney & Goertz, 2006). If the organizations shared common enablers of disability inclusion across these different contexts, we would be more confident that they were generalizable across contexts (cf.

Stake, 1995; Yin, 2011). In Table 2 we provide an overview of the five organizations.

Table 2

Setting, Demographics, and Samples

	USA		Netherlands		Denmark
Company	Walgreens	Sephora	Philips	Vodafone-Ziggo	Grundfos
Facility	Distribution center	Distribution center	Manufacturing	Telecom Service	Manufacturing water pumps
Total employees	225,000	39,000	5,000 and 3,400*	6,500	19,500
Participants	15	21	9	11	10

* Two locations at Philips.

These five organizations are large, private, and successful companies recognized for their inclusion of people with disabilities. Based on knowledge and experience of the authors in the different countries, the cases were selected. The diversification of sectors across all countries was considered. In each of the organizations, we interviewed managers, supervisors, and employees with and without disabilities. We selected employees such as HR project leaders, team managers and team members who had the greatest knowledge and exposure to recruitment and workplace integration. The interviews were semi-structured and lasted from 20 to 60 minutes with the researchers taking notes on the employee responses. All the interviews were transcribed and broken down into units by using collection and coding methods outlined by Strass and Corbin (1990). We analyzed and coded our information by using our field notes, interview transcriptions and conducting member checks. The member checks consisted of checking the validity of interview findings and interpretations with the respondents and collecting additional information. These member checks helped us achieve research trustworthiness by making sure our analysis did not contain researcher bias. In the following, we briefly present the national

context of disability employment and the case organizations.

Walgreens and Sephora (USA)

In the liberalistic business climate in the USA, organizations have a large freedom of discretion to decide if they want to employ people with disabilities. However, the government did pass the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) that prohibits discrimination based on disability in employment. American organizations typically hire disabled citizens based on the business benefit and rationale. They take the economic rationality perspective instead of a social legitimacy perspective (Bousquet, El Haddad & Moore, 2023). Overall, one disabled American citizen in five is employed (US Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2019).

Walgreens is a national pharmacy and started an inclusive initiative with the startup of two new distribution centers in South Carolina and Connecticut in 2010. Among the 550 employees in the two distribution centers, 220 are employees with disabilities (40 percent). The inclusive vision was championed by Randy Lewis a Senior Vice President who wanted to create a business environment where employees with disabilities would be able to work side by side and doing the same level for the same pay as employees without disabilities (Lewis, 2014).

Seeing the success of this inclusive organization **Sephora**, a multinational retailer of personal care and beauty products, followed suit in 2017 by integrating employees with disabilities to an existing distribution center in Mississippi and bringing inclusion to a distribution center startup in Nevada. Among the 400 employees in the distribution centers, 105 are employees with disabilities (26 percent). We studied the four distribution centers, two at Walgreens and two at Sephora (Moore & Hanson, 2023; Moore, Hanson & Maxey, 2022). The distribution centers were studied over five years, through on-site visits and interviews as well as online and in-person member checks. Findings were gathered through

talking with executives, distribution centers general managers, human resource staff, managers, supervisors, and employees about their inclusive workplace reality.

Philips and VodafoneZiggo (The Netherlands)

The institutional context in the Netherlands is characterized by strong labor market regulation, which is the product of negotiations between the government and social parties (employers' organizations and trade unions). In the Netherlands there is a large gap in the employment rate between people with (46%) and without disabilities (78%) (UWV, 2020). To stimulate employers to hire people with disabilities, the Participation Act came into force in 2015 and aims at everyone with capacity to work that are out of work. The Participation Act sets out the framework for this support, while local authorities have the freedom to determine how they wish to guide the target groups into work, and which instruments they deploy to this end. In the 'Guaranteed job agreement' Dutch government, employers' organizations and trade unions committed themselves to create 125,000 extra jobs for people with reduced work capacity before 2026 compared to 2013 (100,000 in the private sector and 25,000 in the public sector). If employers do not create the agreed number of jobs, a quota can be activated (Disability Employment Targets and Quotas Act).

Founded in 1891, **Philips** is a global manufacturer of electronic devices, medical systems, and lighting products. Philips is acknowledged as an inclusive employer that takes care of their employees and the local community. Philips' societal inclusion program is the Philips Employment Plan (WGP). This program allows job seekers with a distance to the labor market, such as people with disabilities, to gain work experience within Philips for a year, combined with a solid development program. The WGP was set up in 1983 to make this group of jobseekers more promising for the labor market, so that afterwards they can find a regular job inside or outside Philips. The WGP is part of Philips' broader vision on Inclusion & Diversity. Philips has many different locations of which we visited two. The

first location employs 5,000 employees and includes 38 employees with a disability. The second location employs 3,400 employees and includes 37 employees with a disability. Although this number might not seem very high, it is influenced by the government definition of a person with a disability (so there may be many more, but they do not count). Philips also intend to train people with disabilities, build their CV within one year to find employment elsewhere, which means that the in- and outflow of people with disabilities is relatively high.

VodafoneZiggo is a Dutch provider of cable television, internet, and mobile telephony. In 2017, the company was created as a merger between the Dutch activities of Liberty Global and Vodafone. The organization embraces differences and states that various backgrounds and perspectives lead to richer ideas, new services, and better results. The company has many initiatives focusing on breaking the barriers around gender, LGBT+, disability, multiculturalism, and age. VodafoneZiggo believes the key to this is increasing awareness of unconscious bias and offer face-to-face training, along with e-learning, webinars, and events to highlight key areas that bias can creep into the workplace and form barriers. VodafoneZiggo employs 6,500 employees and includes 160 employees with a disability.

Grundfos (Denmark)

The Danish labor market is a hybrid between the liberalistic US labor market and the more regulated Dutch labor market. In Denmark, labor market regulations are relatively flexible and employment protection regulation is limited even for workers with disabilities. Relatively generous income security and active labor market policies compensates for the job insecurity created by the flexible labor market (Bredgaard & Madsen, 2018). However, anti-discrimination laws prohibit unfair dismissal and provide rights to reasonable accommodation at work for people with disabilities (Lisberg, 2011). In 2020, the

employment rate of people with disabilities was 55 percent compared to 84 percent for people without disabilities (Larsen et al., 2021).

Grundfos started to include people with disabilities in their production facilities long before these changes in the policy context. Grundfos is one of the world's largest water pump manufacturers with an annual output of more than 17 million units. Grundfos has around 19,500 employees in 56 countries and has headquarters in the small town of Bjerringbro in central Jutland. Founded in 1945 by Poul Due Jensen, the company is owned by the Grundfos foundation, the employees and the founder's family, with the foundation as the primary owner. Grundfos has more than 50 years of experience in employing people with reduced work capacity and was the first Danish company to establish a sheltered workshop within the company for people with intellectual disabilities. Grundfos is inspired by the UN and EU definitions of disability, but finds the translation and measurement of disability challenging in an increasingly global setting. At Grundfos, a disabled person is defined as a person with a permanent limitation in the ability to work because of e.g., physical, mental, or psychological impairments. The person cannot work on equal terms with other employees without job adaptations, like special aids, reduction in working hours or pace. Currently, Grundfos employs more than 600 employees with reduced work capacity due to attrition or disability, which is equivalent to 3.15 percent of the total number of employees. The objective is to reach 5 percent globally by 2025.

FINDINGS

In the analysis, we identify the common enablers of disability inclusive work organizations. We started by identifying the enablers cited in the literature review. In addition to these enablers, we captured common themes articulated by participants about key enablers that supported inclusion in their organization. In the following, we describe

the four common enablers we identified with examples from the five disability inclusive organizations.

(1) *Inclusive core values*

At the heart of all five companies, we find company core values care for others that are vibrant. Many companies have core values that are just words in a strategy document. In these workplaces, they are lived out and cherished. One reason for this is that employees with disabilities have overcome so many hardships and provide an example of resilience, positive outlook, courage, and tenacity that is inspirational to those who take the time to develop an authentic relationship with them (Moore, Hankins & Doughty, 2021). In the two case studies from the USA, the core values of caring for others are lived out in transformed teams. A respondent at Walgreens state:

“We have empathy for the marginalized. This is the only opportunity that might ever be given them.”

At Walgreens and Sephora, employees volunteer to become champions and are the first point of contact for coaching employees with a disability (Moore, Hanson & Maxey, 2022). The Dutch case study shows that team members are the ones who are empathic, patient, and willing to help. At Vodafone, an employee state:

“We are a customer service team and all of us are service oriented individuals. We take care of our team members and make sure that everybody feels at home.”

Vodafone have volunteer team members who are ‘buddies’ that provide the first line of support in the workplace to those with a disability. This reciprocal team dynamic strengthens the commitment to the core value of caring for others through their mutual actions creating an inclusive culture.

In the Danish case, the core values of Grundfos are ‘love for your neighbor’ and ‘care for people’, which have been hallmarks of the company since its foundation. The founder Poul Due Jensen had a motto that is still alive today:

“You must believe that you are something, and no matter what you are, then you are capable of doing something that we can benefit from.”

Poul Due Jensen grew up at a poorhouse in the village Sahl, where his parents were managers, and he got a sound knowledge of how it was to work with the most vulnerable groups in society. To this day, these inclusive core values are still communicated and alive in the organization.

(2) Senior management commitment

To activate inclusive core values, senior management commitment is a necessary condition. In all five organizations, we found there was a senior management commitment in recruiting and retaining workers with disabilities. Without senior management commitment, inclusive core values may wither away and lose relevance in a changing context.

At Sephora, the new CEO, included this inclusive initiative as part of the company’s strategy and aligned institutional resources and efforts to accomplish its goal. It sparks enthusiastic commitment from leaders and supervisors:

“What I have seen is leaders wanting to be part of something special, where they can feel they can have a positive impact on a person's life as part of their job as supervisor.”

At Walgreens, the Senior Vice President of Operations was the executive champion who provided the executive support for launching and operationalizing the inclusive hiring initiative. Corporate sponsorship leads to determining the key performance indicators

(KPIs), staffing, and budget of the inclusion program.

At Philips, their WGP program is firmly established in their corporate strategy long before the Dutch government introduced the Participation Act, which mandates companies to hire people with disabilities. However, the performance of employees with disabilities are not part of the KPI's. This means that departments who hire people with disabilities are not held accountable when the overall (financial) targets are not met. VodafoneZiggo have expanded the inclusive initiative to treating everyone equally breaking barriers of gender, disability, ethnicity, and age.

In Grundfos, there is a long history of CSR and commitment to disability inclusiveness. In 1968, Grundfos was the first Danish company to establish a sheltered workshop (called flex-department) within the company. Initially, the flex-department were employing persons with intellectual disabilities, now they are mainly used to retain employees with reduced work capacity due to attrition or disability. As Grundfos has grown from a medium-sized Danish company to a multi-national company, senior management have insisted on preserving and developing the legacy of disability inclusiveness even in new production facilities abroad. In the current strategy period, Grundfos is transforming its social responsibility to align with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG).

(3) Disability inclusive culture

Related to inclusive core values and senior management commitment, we identified disability inclusive work cultures as important enablers in the five organizations. Disability inclusive cultures are the actual implementation and embodiment of inclusive core values and corporate commitment. It includes the values and actions of middle managers, supervisors and colleagues in the work setting of the disabled employee. In a disability inclusive work setting, disabled workers are treated and managed with respect and equal opportunity.

In the case study of Walgreens' distribution center in Connecticut (USA), we found that the inclusion of people with disabilities dramatically altered the culture in the workplace (Moore, Hanson & Maxey, 2020). Disability inclusion altered the organizational culture, specifically making autocratic managers become people-focused with relationship-based leadership styles. The author also studied the impact of inclusion on teams and discovered that managers showed mindfulness and empathy in developing authentic relationships with their employees (Moore, Maxey, Waite & Wendover, 2020). Employee openness and safe attachments increased employee engagement, adaptability, innovation, and resiliency while exceeding performance metrics. The inclusive teams also adapted to the unique disabilities existing among team members and became self-organizing and adaptive. Key to supporting this transformation was the development of onboarding training in partnership with local supporting agencies (Maxey, Moore & Hanson, 2017). Managers play a central role in all the case studies to facilitate the effectiveness of the employees with disabilities through supporting healthy team cultures. At Walgreens and Sephora, employees with a disability are part of the core business of the organization.

In the Netherlands, respondents describe successful inclusive managers as authentic, patient and involved. At Philips, the managers decide who will join their team. The management of the WGP program stresses that managers must be authentic people managers, who are willing to help and guide others.

“You must make sure you have the time, if you are very busy on your production floor, you should not hire someone from the WGP program. It is not good for the person and not good for the team.”

At VodafoneZiggo, managers have the freedom to make the choice themselves to hire someone with a disability. Vodafone team managers signal that team members include people with disabilities in the group quickly and adjust their behavior accordingly and that

there is great enthusiasm by colleagues:

“The willingness to become a buddy is greater than we needed. That is our strength.”

At Grundfos, the disability inclusive culture is the result of the core values of ‘care for people’ (people-centered management) and management commitment to inclusiveness and social responsibility. In interviews with the senior manager on CSR, it was clear that the original disability inclusive culture at Grundfos was challenged by the globalization of the company and the competition for market shares. The tension became visible in the job design in the flex departments. Originally, employees with intellectual disabilities performed simple, repetitive manual tasks in internal jobs that were reserved for them (e.g., assembly work, emptying dustbins, assisting in the canteen). While many companies have outsourced or automatized such activities to reduce expenditures, Grundfos tries to keep these jobs and services inhouse as they are suitable for employees with disabilities that cannot perform ordinary jobs. Grundfos also strive to integrate workers with disabilities in the ordinary production in the company but finds it difficult to balance social concerns with performance and production metrics. To bridge this gap Danish companies, have access to wage subsidy programs that subsidize the employer for the reduced work ability of a person with disabilities, e.g., flexjobs (Bredgaard, 2020).

(4) Community partnerships

In all five organizations, we identified an enabler, which was not clearly identified in the literature review, namely: community partnerships. Community partners can be local community organizations, disability organizations, and public employment services, who are the experts or authorities with the experience in assisting individuals with disabilities develop workplace skills. They collaborate through knowledge sharing and providing

personnel who assist in the development of training, job design, onboarding programs, and hands-on job coaching.

In the Walgreens case, local government organizations serving the needs of the disabled partnered with Walgreens to develop a transitional work group (TWG) as a pre-hiring 9-week onboarding program (Maxey, Moore & Hanson, 2017). This pre-hire training program assists employees with disabilities to execute core business functions. The TWG program aims to help candidates with a disability to demonstrate technical tasks and soft skills such as teamwork, conflict resolution, and overall job readiness (Maxey, Moore & Hanson, 2017). Sephora acknowledges the importance of state involvement but are not currently satisfied with the collaboration:

“I have learned that the state is a key enabler. The government agency for the disabled failed us because they were unwilling/unable to change their processes. We are in the process of building a structure that can function without their connectivity in the local communities.”

In the Netherlands, Philips' WGP program works closely with the municipality and the Public Employment Service (UWV) to bring knowledge and expertise to the company. The HR manager is in regular contact with them and play a broker role in matching candidates with team managers. VodafoneZiggo uses partner agencies for finding candidates who are a match for the job posting. However, they have hired job coaches as VodafoneZiggo employees to provide better support to employees with disabilities and their managers. In both Dutch cases, the length of the contract for employees with disabilities is only one year, after which they need to find new employment.

In Denmark, Grundfos has a long-standing partnership with public employment services, local authorities, and the local community. The local authorities collaborate with Grundfos to match unemployed jobseekers with disabilities as well as other groups (e.g., ethnic minorities and refugees) with vacancies and to carve out jobs for people with

disabilities. Due to its role as the major local employer and its commitment to disability inclusion, Grundfos has also hired an internal social advisor that performs work assessments, interviews, and job design.

DISCUSSION

At the heart of all five companies, we found inclusive core values that extend beyond economic values and includes social and societal purposes (cf. Gilbride et al., 2003). To activate inclusive core values, senior management commitment is a necessary condition (cf. Chan et al., 2020). The actual implementation and embodiment of inclusive core values and senior management commitment is found in a disability inclusive culture in which disabled workers are treated and managed with respect and equal opportunity (cf. Collela, 1994; Hagner et al., 2014; Medina & Gamero, 2017). Finally, we identified community partnerships as an enabler, which was not as clearly identified in the existing literature. These partnerships include local community organizations, disability organizations, and public employment services and include collaboration on training, job design, onboarding programs and job coaching. A similar finding is alluded to in the literature on Individual Placement and Support (Drake & Bond, 2014; Suijkerbuijk et al., 2017) and supported employment (Bond, 2004; Bond et al., 2008).

Disability inclusive work organizations also face tensions and challenges. Tensions and challenges can stimulate organizations to find innovative solutions or become disabling and unproductive. The basic tension we identified was the balance between economic and social values. At Walgreens and Sephora, the hiring of employees with disabilities has become a key performance indicator for their distribution centers, which can conflict with the need for productivity. In both cases, managers hire disabled employees as well as ensuring that employee productivity metrics are reached (Hanson & Moore, 2023). In the Dutch and Danish cases, there was also a tension between the performance improvement

plans and the measurement of key performance indicators. In Denmark, Grundfos is struggling to retain the tradition of disability inclusion and CSR while expanding to new global markets. The integration and retention of employees with disabilities comes with costs and is not necessarily profitable in the short term. This may produce internal tensions where coworkers and supervisors become skeptical and critical of disability inclusion.

In this study, we have identified the common enablers of disability inclusive work organizations across very different institutional and national contexts. We suggest that other organizations that intend to become disability inclusive or community organizations that intend to persuade employers to recruit and retain employees with disabilities, should examine their core values, management commitments, work cultures and partnerships. These enablers have emerged from the experiences and practices of companies that have proven successful in including employees with disabilities.

We suggest that rather than focusing on barriers we can learn to facilitate the labor market integration of persons with disabilities by studying the enablers of disability inclusive work organizations. In future research, we invite researchers to test these enablers of disability inclusive work organizations in a larger population through quantitative research methods and determine the relationships between enablers to the successful hiring of disabled employees. This would provide evidence to build solid and cross-disciplinary models and theories of disability inclusive work organizations.

CONCLUSION

Persons with disabilities have significantly lower employment and higher inactivity rates compared to people without disabilities and are more likely to work in precarious and atypical jobs. To better understand how to include more people with disabilities in the labor market, we have explored the common characteristics of disability inclusive work organizations. The study is based on a strategic selection of companies that employ a much

larger proportion of employees with disabilities compared to similar companies in their country: Walgreens and Sephora in the USA, Philips and VodafoneZiggo in the Netherlands and Grundfos in Denmark. They are large, private, and successful companies in very different contexts. Across three most different national and institutional contexts and five different private organizations, we identified four specific enablers of disability inclusive work organizations: (1) inclusive core values, (2) senior management commitment, (2) disability inclusive cultures and (4) community partnerships. The enablers are related and mutually reinforcing. The findings from our case studies are consistent with the existing research on disability and employment and adds to our understanding of the relationships between the enablers of disability inclusive work organizations.

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